

ANALYSIS OF THE STORY 'LUCKY ARTISTAND' BY ENGLISH AUTHOR SOMERSET MAUGHAM

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Annotation: Analyzing the artistic work by its form and content, it is possible to show the author's approach to the work. This article analyzes the English writer Somerset Maugham's 'Lucky Artistand' story by its form and content components.

Key words: Theme, idea, character, plot, exposition, knot, development of events, solution, culmination, composition, language.

In the fiction the content and form balance is important and this enables to evaluate its value. According to L.Timofeev's theory, the components of the form and content are classified: theme, idea, character- content elements, plot, composition, language- form elements. For above mentioned classification, this article analyze the famous English author, Somerset Maugham's story, 'Lucky artistand'. When it comes to the events of the work, they mainly held in Paris and New York. Charlie Bartle, the hero of the work, was languishing and being disappointed by his excessive poverty and insecurity in terms of artistic works. One day his neighbour from downstairs, Mr. Leir knocked on Charlie's door, came and chatted with him. The old man made friend with a lot of painters during his lifetime. He would be able to know before a long time than others, that the works of impressionist artists will make a profit in the future and purchased them as soon as possible. The multitude of such kind of artists have been saved from poverty and slavery.

Later, when the great French painters such as Mane, Mone, and Sisley were known to all people, Mr. Leir was one of the richest men, due to the fact that, he

sold those pictures for a great deal of money. Now the old man have finished up his sales. His single daughter was married to a merchant from New York city, who is doing with painting-sale. During the conversation between the neighbors, Charlie was talking about the problems, he was suffering. To be exact, tomorrow he should give three hundred francs for his apartment and his girl-friend, Rosa's father opposed to their marriage until Charlie has five thousand francs in the bank (Because Rosa had so much money in her account) and the annual income consists of two hundred fifty francs. In order to help unprecedented artist, Mr. Leir was going to send Charlie's work to his son-in-law, Rudolf and while looking through the Charlie's pictures, he came across a wonderful work and surprised. He thought that is the work of the great French artist Vatto. Ch. Bartle said that he had just copied with the old British lady's collection and a month later, the old woman's house was a fire, as a result, all the collections have been burnt. When Mr. Leir wanted to buy the picture, Charlie announced that he had to sell him for the sake of pledging that he wouldn't show as original one. Mr. Leir said that if he is worried about this, he can be dye Vatto's name and put his own signature.

After buying the picture, he sent it his son-in-law and forward a message about customs lawyer has recently received Vatto's original picture had been faked by Charlie Bartle. If Bartle's name is removed, he will be witness that. Anyhow Rudolf was able to take the picture for a large sum and a fine. This event is followed by noise in the newspapers, as well as, shortly a man purchase it for sixty thousand dollars.

Two weeks later, Mr. Leir went to the young artist's home and put five thousand pounds. He told the story from the beginning. Even Charlie was amazed to hear that Leir sold his other works to a rich man from California. After returning home, Mr. Leir took Charli Bartle's other works from the wardrobe and threw into the fireplace. The old man smiled being happy to see the paintings warm up at least. But he had completely forgotten that his five thousand pounds had been presented willingly a few minutes ago. By analyzing the story according to Timofeev's classification, a young artist's life was taken up as a social- modern

point for theme. The story reveals the idea of an old man being drawn to young artist, helping him to leave the desperate situation, making him happy, rebuilding his confidence to the future. Heroes that have been raised to character level include Charlie Bartle, Mr. Leir, and Rosa's father. Throughout Charlie Bartle's character is summarized as an inexperienced, lively, gullible guy in terms of coming across difficult situation. Mr. Leir is a master of his work, an intelligent, generous man, who works for the benefit of others and his, sometimes tricky, but due to the aspect, he helps many people to find their place in life as a person. As for Rosa's father, he measures happiness with money or just thinks of his daughter's future (because all parents want their children to see in happy days) and shows parents' inner feelings. The components of the form are listed in the following analysis. According to the plot components, the exposition is given like that 'Charlie Bartle, is able to move from complicated circumstances easily. And his workshop, is situated in Ryu Berd Street isn't seen so awful...' Rosa's father's disagreement about Charlie and her marriage and the inability of a young artist to copy with poverty and insecurity makes the knot. As the development of events, Mr. Leir is an example of Charlie Bartle's work and conversation with him. The purchase of the young painter's work creates culmination of the story. Mr. Leir's contribution to selling Charlie's paintings and coming true dream of young artist is considered solution. The story isn't defective in terms of composition, the title is very suitable for theme as 'Lucky artistand'. Portraits and landscaping techniques are widely used in the story. When it comes to the language of the work, the use of letters and dialogues in communication among heroes involve a positive effect on the content of the work. In summary, the story is able to meet the prose demands in every respect. For L. Timofeev's classification, the elements of the form and content are fully complied with.

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